

STUDIES ON SULPHONAMIDES AND ANALOGOUS COMPOUNDS

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Certain sulphonamides and sulphones have been prepared and described.

It has been recently noticed by Swyer and Young (*Brit. Med. J.*, 1945, i, 149) and Bose and Ghosh (*Indian Med. Gaz.*, 1945, 80, 293) that N¹-benzoylsulphanilamide exerts a specific chemotherapeutic action against bacillary dysentery organisms. This compound is readily absorbed from the gastro-intestinal tract (*cf.* Bose and Ghosh, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1944, 32, 61); but it is the general belief that the efficacy of a sulphanilamide type of compound in bacillary dysentery is dependent on its low solubility and poor absorption from the upper alimentary tract (Marshall *et al.*, *Bull. Johns Hopk. Hosp.*, 1940, 67, 163; 68, 94). On this hypothesis certain acyl derivatives of sulphathiazol were also prepared and found to be effective (*cf.* Poth and Ross, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1944, 29, 785). It was considered to be of interest to study the influence of similar acyl substituents at the *para*-amino group of N¹-benzoylsulphanilamide. Accordingly, N¹-acetyl-, -benzoyl-, -succinyl-, and -phthalyl derivatives were prepared and their bacteriostatic action against bacillary dysentery organisms (Flexner Y.) was noted.

As amidino group exerts a parasitocidal action, it was then introduced into the above sulphanilylbenzamide by replacement of its *p*-amino group. The resulting *p*-amidinobenzene sulphonbenzoylamide hydrochloride (II), the simple *p*-amidinobenzene sulphonamide hydrochloride (III) and the *p*-amidinophenylmethylsulphone hydrochloride (IV) were all studied. Recently the antibacterial activity of the compounds (III) and (IV) and *p*-(aminomethyl)-phenylmethylsulphone hydrochloride (V) has been recorded by Evans, Fuller and Walker (*Lancet*, 1944, ii, 523) against gas gangrene. These compounds were also prepared and their bacteriostatic action on dysentery organisms noted. In searching the literature it was noticed that the action of the simple sulphone, *p*-aminophenylmethylsulphone (VI) has not been studied against bacillary dysentery and as such this compound was also prepared (*cf.* Fourneau *et al.*, *Compt. rend. soc. Biol.*, 1938, 127, 393) and its *in vitro* activity was studied.

The antibacterial action of the above compounds were studied on the organism of bacillary dysentery (Flexner Y) by noting the inhibition of growth in a culture medium made from a papain-digest-glucose-phosphate broth when incubated for 72 hours at 37°. In each case the inoculum used was about 1000 organisms in 5 c. c. of broth. The table below shows the minimal concentration expressed in mg. of drug per 100 c. c. of culture medium.

Minimal inhibiting concentration in mg. of drug per 100 c.c. of culture medium.										
Organism	Compounds									
	(I)	(II)	(III)	(IV)	(V)	(VI)	Ac	Bz	Succ	Phthal
Flexner (Y)	10	100	100	100	20	100	100	100	100	200

Ac = Acetyl
Bz = Benzoyl
Succ = Succinyl
Phthal = Phthalyl } derivative of sulphanilylbenzamide.

It is evident from the table that none of the various compounds studied is superior to sulphanilylbenzamide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sulphanilylbenzamide (N¹-Benzoylsulphanilamide) (I).—At first acetyl sulphanilylbenzamide was prepared by modified Schotten-Baumann method from *p*-acetylsulphanilamide and benzoyl chloride. The compound crystallised from dilute alcohol in needles, m. p. 251° (decomp.) (cf. Crossley *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 61, 2950). (Found: N, 9.11. Calc for C₁₄H₁₄O₄N₂S: N, 8.805 per cent).

The N⁴-acetylsulphanilylbenzamide was then hydrolysed by heating on a water-bath with caustic soda solution (6%) for 1 hour. The cold solution was just neutralised with dilute hydrochloric acid when sulphanilylbenzamide precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from rectified spirit in prisms, m. p. 181-82° (cf. Crossley *et al.*, *loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 10.4. Calc for C₁₃H₁₂O₃N₂S: N, 10.15 per cent).

*N*⁴-Benzoylsulphanilylbenzamide was prepared by benzoylating sulphanilylbenzamide by the Schotten-Baumann method as above. On acidifying the alkaline solution of the benzoylated product, the dibenzoyl derivative precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with water and then boiled with water, filtered hot and washed with hot water. The product was then crystallised from alcohol. It melted at 258° (decomp.) (cf. Chien-Pen-Lo, *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 660) (Found: N, 7.54. Calc for C₂₀H₁₆O₄N₂S: N 7.37 per cent).

*N*⁴-Succinylsulphanilylbenzamide.—Finely powdered succinic anhydride (1 mol.) was gradually added to a boiling suspension of sulphanilylbenzamide (1 mol.) in absolute alcohol. After the addition was over, the solution was refluxed for 1 hour on a water-bath. A crystalline solid separated out. The product was cooled, filtered, washed with a little alcohol and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 214°. (Found: N, 7.61. C₁₇H₁₄O₄N₂S requires N, 7.45 per cent).

*N*⁴-Phthalylsulphanilylbenzamide.—Sulphanilylbenzamide (5g.) was dissolved in 50 c. c. of absolute alcohol by boiling and freshly sublimed and finely powdered phthalic anhydride (2.7 g.) was added in small quantities at a time to the boiling solution. The solution was then refluxed for 2 hours and cooled. A white crystalline compound separated. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from acetone, m. p. 224-25°. (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.56. C₂₁H₁₆O₄N₂S requires N, 6.6 per cent).

p-Amidinoulphanilylbenzamide *Hydrochloriae* (II).—Powdered *p*-cyanosulphanilylbenzamide (7 g.) (prepared by benzoylating *p*-cyanosulphanilamide in our modified Schotten-Baumann method) was dissolved in 300 c. c. of absolute alcohol and dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed through the solution, cooled in ice, till saturated. The solution was then kept in the refrigerator for 4 days. A white crystalline compound separated which was filtered, washed with absolute alcohol, powdered and added to 50 c. c. of alcohol, saturated with ammonia gas and the solution was kept at the room temperature for 6 days. A crystalline compound separated. It was filtered, washed with alcohol and crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m. p. 210-11°. (Found: N, 12.62; Cl, 10.24. C₁₄H₁₂O₃N₂S, HCl requires N, 12.37; Cl, 10.45 per cent).

p-Amidinobenzeneulphanilamide *Hydrochloride* (III).—*p*-Cyano-sulphanilamide was dissolved in absolute alcohol and proceeding exactly in the same manner as in the previous example, the *p*-amidinobenzene-sulphonamide was isolated. The substance was crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid, m. p. 242-44°. (Found: N, 17.98; Cl, 14.82. C₇H₆O₂N₂S, HCl requires N, 17.83; Cl, 15.07 per cent).

p-Amidinophenylmethylsulphone Hydrochloride (IV).

(i) *Acetylaminophenylmethylsulphone*.—Finely powdered sodium salt of *p*-acetylaminobenzenesulphonic acid (I) (Organic Syntheses, Vol. V, p. 1) was suspended in alcohol. Methyl iodide dissolved in alcohol was added drop by drop to the boiling suspension of the sodium sulphinate. After the addition was over the solution was refluxed for 1 hour. It was then filtered, the alcohol evaporated off from the filtrate and the solid residue thus obtained was treated with water, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from water, as white needles, m. p. 186–87°. (Found : N, 6.69. $C_9H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 6.57 per cent).

(ii) *p*-Aminophenylmethylsulphone.—*p*-Acetylaminophenylmethylsulphone was refluxed with 25 times its weight of 10% hydrochloric acid for 1 hour. The solution was cooled, filtered and neutralised with dilute ammonia. The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from water in small plates, m. p. 137°. (Found : N, 8.26. $C_7H_9O_2NS$ requires N, 8.18 per cent).

(iii) *p*-Cyanophenylmethylsulphone.—*p*-Aminophenylmethylsulphone was diazotised in the usual way and the diazotised solution was treated with copper cyanide in potassium cyanide solution with stirring. Then the mixture was heated to 70° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, cooled and filtered. The product thus obtained was crystallised from a large volume of water as colourless needles, m. p. 144–45°. (Found : N, 7.85. $C_7H_7O_2NS$ requires N, 7.73 per cent).

(iv) *p*-Amidinophenylmethylsulphone hydrochloride was prepared in the usual method as described in the preparation of *p*-amidinosulphanylbenzamide and crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid. It melted at 288°. (Found : N, 12.06 ; Cl, 14.83. $C_8H_{10}O_2N_2S$, HCl requires N, 11.94 ; Cl, 15.1 per cent).

p-Aminomethylphenylmethylsulphone Hydrochloride (V).—Benzyl acetamide was treated with chlorosulphonic acid in the usual way. The sulpho-chloride thus obtained was reduced with sodium sulphite (cf. "Organic Syntheses", Vol. V, p. 1) and the sulphonic acid was converted into the sodium salt. The sodium salt of *p*-(acetyl-amino-methyl) benzene sulphonic acid was boiled with alcohol and an alcoholic solution of methyl iodide was added drop by drop. After the addition was over the solution was refluxed for 1 hour, filtered, and the alcohol evaporated off. The solid residue thus obtained was treated with water, filtered, washed with water and dried. It had a melting point of 122°. The crude product was directly hydrolysed by refluxing for 1 hour with 25 times its weight of dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution was filtered and concentrated

by evaporation and cooled when a crystalline compound separated. It was filtered, washed with a little water and crystallised from water in flakes, m. p: 265°. (Found: N, 6.44; Cl, 15.7. $C_8H_{11}O_2NS$, HCl requires N, 6.32; Cl, 16.02 per cent).

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